

Robust CBF-based STL motion planning for socially responsible robot navigation in the presence of measurement noise*

Andrea Ruo, Lorenzo Sabattini and Valeria Villani

Abstract—In recent years, an increasing number of service robots have been deployed in human environments. The growing complexity of modern robotic systems and the environments in which they operate necessitates careful consideration of safety, increasing the challenges associated with socially responsible navigation. Moreover, localization measurements are often affected by random noise, which can lead to unsafe behavior if not addressed in the control design. Therefore, it is crucial to ensure robustness against measurement noise. This paper addresses navigation challenges by presenting a robust CBF-based STL motion planning algorithm, integrated with an unscented Kalman filter. This methodology mitigates the effects of state disturbances and measurement noise, ensuring task completion at any time within a specified time interval for dynamic systems subject to nonlinear velocity constraints and collision avoidance. A simulation study is conducted to validate the methodology, demonstrating its ability to ensure safety.

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, numerous service robots have been employed to serve a wide range of practical purposes, including application in healthcare [1], museums [2], and airports [3]. In particular, roles like reception and guidance have become increasingly popular, giving rise to the concept of socially responsible navigation (SRN). It implies that robots navigate among humans and might interact with them or carry out a task that takes into account the presence of humans. These conditions pose different challenges. First, safety is a primary concern, since the robot must plan and execute a collision-free path, and reduce its speed in proximity of humans [4]–[6]. Another aspect to consider is the robot’s behavior in deadlock situations [7]. In intersections or narrow doorways, the robot can either take the initiative to go first or proactively propose a solution by, for example, making a gesture, emitting a signal to allow others to pass first. Additionally, the robot may need to follow a person [8] or be followed, to guide them to a target destination [9]. In this case, the robot should keep the user within its field of view, reduce its speed if the human is slowing down or stop if the person is no longer following. Furthermore, there might be the need for the robot to recognize the person it is interacting with (or following or guiding) and adjust its behavior, such as speed, to accommodate individual preferences. Additionally, in social environments where robots and people coexist and robots move according to human needs, space-time constraints might be useful to guarantee the efficient and

safe execution of activities satisfying human requirements, for example in terms of temporal deadlines.

Specifically, in this work we address an SRN scenario where a robot navigates among humans and static and dynamic obstacles, and is able to reprogram its trajectory, decelerate when approaching obstacles, or accelerate in fully autonomous or obstacle-free areas. Moreover, since it operates in narrow and crowded spaces, the robot should exhibit high maneuverability and agility, as omnidirectional robots do. Additionally, we take into account space-time constraints, such as “*the robot must reach a given position within 20 seconds*” or “*the robot must remain in the area for 5 seconds*”. Lastly, we consider the challenges of operating in unstructured and unknown environments, where the robot’s localization may be subject to inaccuracies.

SRN problems with spatio-temporal constraints in the presence of obstacles have been partially addressed in [4], [6], where we presented a control barrier function-based signal temporal logic (CBF-based STL) motion planning algorithm that guarantees task completion at any time within a specified interval. This approach relies on the combination between STL, to specify spatial-temporal constraints, and CBF, to guarantee safe navigation. STL is a temporal logic formalism that enables the specification of spatio-temporal constraints, as demonstrated in [10]–[12]. With respect to safety, CBFs have recently gained considerable attention for their role in safety-critical applications. By defining a forward-invariant safe set through barrier functions and solving for control input using quadratic programming, CBFs ensure that the system remains within the safe set [13]. Nevertheless, the approach proposed in [4], [6] considers an ideal case where the robot model is known and no disturbances are present. However, to apply these methods in real-world scenarios, the presence of noise in state and output measurements cannot be ignored. An unreliable localization measurement can lead to unsafe behavior if it is not accounted for in the control design. Therefore, it is crucial to consider robustness against measurement noise.

In [14], the authors proposed a framework for safety-critical control of systems with erroneous state estimates. This framework leverages CBFs and unifies the method of backup sets for synthesizing control invariant sets with robustness requirements. The outcome is the synthesis of measurement-robust CBFs, which provide guarantees for safe behavior in the presence of imperfect measurements. The works in [15], [16] considered robust CBF formulations with worst-case disturbance bounds to ensure safety. Specifically, in [15], the authors introduced the concept

*This work was supported by Horizon Europe program under the Grant Agreement 101070351 (SERMAS).

Department of Sciences and Methods for Engineering (DISMI), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Italy {name.surname}@unimore.it

of robust-CBF, which, when combined with input-to-state stable control Lyapunov functions, yields controllers for constrained nonlinear systems under known, partially known, and unknown disturbances. In [16], the authors proposed a robust control Lyapunov function and a CBF-based quadratic programs (QP) controller with an Unscented Kalman filter (UKF) which has the capability to mitigate the effects of state disturbance and measurement errors. Safety guarantees in the presence of measurement noise were addressed for stochastic systems in [17]. The authors presented a framework for CBFs in stochastic systems subject to Gaussian process and measurement noise. They developed CBFs for environments with incomplete state information, with states estimated via sensors corrupted by Gaussian noise. It has been proven that the proposed CBFs ensure safety when the state estimate is within a specified bound of the true state, a condition achieved using an extended Kalman filter (EKF) when the system is linear or when the process and measurement noise are sufficiently small.

This paper extends the CBF-based STL motion planning methodology, first presented in [4] and [6]. In particular, we propose a robust CBF-based STL motion planning methodology combined with a UKF to mitigate the effects of noise on state measurement. Hence, our methodology ensures task completion at any time within a specified time interval for dynamic systems subject to nonlinear velocity constraints, collision avoidance, and erroneous state measurements.

II. PRELIMINARIES

In the following, scalars are represented by non-bold letters such as x , while vectors are denoted by bold letters like \mathbf{x} . The set of real numbers is denoted by \mathbb{R} , and \mathbb{R}^n represents the n -dimensional real vector space. The set of non-negative and positive real numbers are $\mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ and $\mathbb{R}_{> 0}$, respectively. A class \mathcal{K} function $\alpha : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is a continuous, strictly-increasing function satisfying $\alpha(0) = 0$. Let $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$ be the state and input of a nonlinear input-affine control system:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = f(\mathbf{x}) + g(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{u}, \quad (1)$$

where the functions $f : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $g : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ are locally Lipschitz continuous [11]. For a control signal $\mathbf{u} : [t_0, t_1] \rightarrow \mathcal{U}$, the signal $\mathbf{x} : [t_0, t_1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ is considered a solution to (1) if \mathbf{x} is absolutely continuous and $\mathbf{x}(t)$ satisfies (1) for all $t \in [t_0, t_1]$.

A. Signal Temporal Logic

We employ STL as a temporal logic formalism due to its capability to express both qualitative and quantitative requirements of systems in continuous domains [18]. Consider a continuous-time signal $\mathbf{s} : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$. STL uses logical predicates, denoted by μ , to evaluate the truth values of continuous signals $\mathbf{s}(t)$. These predicates [10] are determined by evaluating a predicate function $h : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as follows:

$$\mu := \begin{cases} \text{True} & \text{if } h(\mathbf{s}(t)) \geq 0 \\ \text{False} & \text{if } h(\mathbf{s}(t)) < 0. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In this work, the continuous signal corresponds to the system's state trajectory at time t , denoted as $\mathbf{x}(t)$. The STL syntax [4] for an STL formula ϕ can be associated with one of the several expressions defined by the grammar in (3):

$$\phi ::= \top \mid \mu \mid \neg\phi \mid \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \mid \phi_1 U_{[a,b]} \phi_2. \quad (3)$$

Specifically, the STL formula ϕ can be associated with: the Boolean True (\top) meaning the formula is always true; the predicate μ , where ϕ is true if the predicate is satisfied, as described in (2); the “negation” operator, where ϕ is true if the negated formula $\neg\phi$ is false; the “conjunction” operator of two STL formulas $\phi_1 \wedge \phi_2$ where ϕ is true when both ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are simultaneously true; or the “until” temporal operator $\phi_1 U_{[a,b]} \phi_2$ where $a, b \in \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ define the bounds of the interval defined by the temporal operator, with $a \leq b$. In this case ϕ is true if ϕ_1 becomes true and remains true within the time interval $[a, b]$ before ϕ_2 becomes true. Additionally, the “eventually” and “always” temporal operators can be introduced, defined as $F_{[a,b]} \phi := \top U_{[a,b]} \phi$, and $G_{[a,b]} \phi := \neg F_{[a,b]} \neg\phi$, where $G_{[a,b]} \phi$ is satisfied if ϕ holds throughout the interval $[a, b]$. The satisfaction relation $(\mathbf{x}, t) \models \phi$ indicates that the signal $\mathbf{x} : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, e.g., a solution of (1), satisfies ϕ at time t . For a more detailed discussion, see [4].

B. CBFs encoding STL formulation

The concept behind CBFs is to design control inputs that guarantee the forward invariance of certain regions for the given dynamical system. This property ensures that the specified set remains forward invariant with respect to the system's dynamics. Consequently, if the system starts within this set, it will always stay within it.

In [12], the authors established a connection between a function $\mathbf{b} : \mathbb{R}^n \times [t_0, t_1] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, later confirmed to be a valid CBF (vCBF), and the STL semantics of ϕ . Specifically, if this function is in accordance with the criteria outlined in [11] (i.e., Steps A, B and C in [11]), then, for a given signal $\mathbf{x} : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ with $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}(t), t) \geq 0$ for all $t \geq 0$, it follows that $(\mathbf{x}, 0) \models \phi$.

Let \mathcal{C} denote the safe set, which represents the configurations that satisfy the system's safety requirements. \mathcal{C} explicitly depends on time

$$\mathcal{C}(t) := \{\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t) \geq 0\}. \quad (4)$$

Hence, $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathcal{C}(t)$ for all $t \geq 0$ implies $(\mathbf{x}, 0) \models \phi$.

When dealing with multiple temporal operators and predicates, we utilize a smooth approximation of the min operator [4] in order to approximate the set of all barriers for each temporal operator into a single one, thereby obtaining the most constraining barrier function. For p functions $\mathbf{b}_l : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ where $l \in \{1, \dots, p\}$, let

$$\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t) := -\frac{1}{\eta} \ln \left(\sum_{l=1}^p \exp(-\eta \mathbf{b}_l(\mathbf{x}, t)) \right) \quad \text{with } \eta > 0. \quad (5)$$

Note that $\min_{l \in \{1, \dots, p\}} \mathbf{b}_l(\mathbf{x}, t) \approx \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ where the precision of this approximation improves as η increases. This is

beneficial because if $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t) \geq 0$, it ensures that $\mathbf{b}_l(\mathbf{x}, t) \geq 0$ for each $l \in \{1, \dots, p\}$.

Under these conditions, it is possible to compute the control input \mathbf{u} that ensures $\mathcal{C}(t)$ remains forward invariant when $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a vCBF, by means of the following QP:

$$\min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{U}} \mathbf{u}^T Q \mathbf{u} \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial \mathbf{x}} (f(\mathbf{x}) + g(\mathbf{x})\mathbf{u}) + \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} \geq -\alpha(\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t)), \quad (6b)$$

where $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ is a positive semi-definite matrix. This convex optimization problem is feasible if $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is a vCBF. For further details, please refer to [4].

C. UKF

The UKF describes a filtering algorithm for estimating the state of a nonlinear system, affected by random noises, based on a sequence of observations and control information [16]. Specifically, we consider the following dynamic nonlinear time-invariant discrete-time system with additive noise:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}_{k+1} &= F(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) + \mathbf{v}_k, \\ \mathbf{y}_k &= H(\mathbf{x}_k) + \mathbf{n}_k, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_k \in \mathbb{R}^n$ denotes the unobserved state of the system at time k , $\mathbf{y}_k \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is the observed measurement signal at time k , \mathbf{v}_k is a zero-mean Gaussian noise process with covariance matrix $Q \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ at time k , \mathbf{n}_k is a zero-mean Gaussian noise observation with covariance matrix $R \in \mathbb{R}^{p \times p}$ at time k , and $\mathbf{u}_k \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the control input at time k . Without loss of generality, we assume here that \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{n} are uncorrelated. F and H are the state transition function and the measurement function respectively [19]. In general, F and H are not linear. In order to estimate the probability distribution of the system's state using efficient Kalman filtering, one has to linearize the functions F and H . While the EKF performs this linearization using Taylor series expansion, which can introduce errors in the posterior mean and covariance, the UKF uses a more accurate stochastic approximation, known as the unscented transformation. This method provides a better estimate of the posterior distribution without requiring linearization, while maintaining the same computational complexity as the EKF [20].

It is possible to estimate the state using the UKF algorithm given in [20], considering that the input is the mean and covariance of the estimate at time k , along with the control input, u_k , and the observation, y_k .

III. PROBLEM STATEMENT

We propose an enhancement to the CBF-STL motion planning algorithm described in [4] and [6], to handle observation signals affected by random noise. Specifically, we introduce a robust CBF-based STL motion planning method combined with UKF. This method ensures that robot navigation tasks are completed at any time within a specified interval for a omnidirectional robot subjected to nonlinear velocity constraints, collision avoidance, and inaccuracies in state measurements.

To achieve this, we utilize the STL fragment discussed in [4] and presented in (8). In particular, we categorize STL formulas into two types: ψ , which defines an elementary class, and ϕ , which defines a composite class that includes temporal operators and conjunctions of multiple elementary STL formulas:

$$\psi ::= \top \mid \mu \mid \neg \mu \mid \psi_1 \wedge \psi_2, \quad (8a)$$

$$\phi ::= G_{[a,b]} \psi \mid F_{[a,b]} \psi \mid \psi_1 U_{[a,b]} \psi_2 \mid \phi_1 \wedge \phi_2 \quad (8b)$$

where ψ_1, ψ_2 are formulas of the class ψ given in (8a), whereas ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are formulas of the class ϕ given in (8b). We make assumptions similar to those presented in [11] and [4].

Assumption 1: For an STL formula ϕ defined according to (8b), there exists a constant $C \geq 0$ such that $(\mathbf{x}, 0) \models \phi \implies \|\mathbf{x}(t)\| \leq C \forall t \geq 0$.

This guarantees that trajectories $\mathbf{x}(t)$ are bounded.

Assumption 2: The vector function $g(\mathbf{x})$ in (1) is such that $g(\mathbf{x})g(\mathbf{x})^T$ is positive definite for all $\mathbf{x} \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Now, the problem under consideration in this paper can be stated as follows.

Problem 1: Given the omnidirectional robot's dynamical system in (1) affected by state measurement errors, where \mathbf{x} represents the position and \mathbf{u} denotes the angular velocities of the wheels, and an STL formula ϕ expressed according to (8), derive a control law $\mathbf{u}(t)$ so that the solution $\mathbf{x} : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ to (1) is such that $(\mathbf{x}, 0) \models \phi$, providing safety guarantees, including the satisfaction of nonlinear velocity constraints and obstacle avoidance.

IV. PROPOSED APPROACH

To solve Problem 1, knowledge of the correct system's state, i.e., the current robot position, is required. In the presence of noise affecting the robot's position, the direct measurement becomes unreliable, necessitating estimation of the state. In this work, state estimation is performed using UKF. The estimated state, in contrast to the noisy measurements, is utilized to compute a vCBF that addresses Problem 1. For this reason, in Sec. IV-A, we explain the formulation used to calculate the estimated states from noisy measurements. Subsequently, in Sec. IV-B we present the proposed robust CBF-STL motion planning methodology.

A. Formulation of UKF

UKF requires a discrete-time state transition function, F in (7), but the robot's model considered in (1) is continuous-time. To compute the discrete-time approximation of the continuous-time model, we rely on the Euler discretization method [21]. Considering the robot's dynamical system in (1), the resulting discrete-time state transition function, defined in (7) is:

$$F(\mathbf{x}_k, \mathbf{u}_k) = \mathbf{x}_k + (f(\mathbf{x}_k) + g(\mathbf{x}_k)\mathbf{u}_k)T_s, \quad (9)$$

where the accuracy of this approximation depends on the sample time T_s . Moreover, we assume that the measurement function, H in (7), is an identity matrix since the robot's output is its position, which coincides with the state.

Following the formulation of UKF [20], the augmented state is defined as the concatenation of the original state \mathbf{x} and noise variables \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{n} :

$$\mathbf{x}^a = [\mathbf{x}^T, \mathbf{v}^T, \mathbf{n}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^L, \text{ with } L = 2n + p. \quad (10)$$

The UKF is initialized with:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0 = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}_0], \quad (11)$$

$$P_0 = \mathbb{E}[(\mathbf{x}_0 - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0)(\mathbf{x}_0 - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0)^T], \quad (12)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^a = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}_0^a] = [\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^T, 0^T, 0^T]^T, \quad (13)$$

$$P_0^a = \mathbb{E}[(\mathbf{x}_0^a - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^a)(\mathbf{x}_0^a - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^a)^T] = \begin{bmatrix} P_0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & Q & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R \end{bmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

where \mathbb{E} is the expected value, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$ is the initial state estimation, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^a$ is the initial augmented state estimation, while $P_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $P_0^a \in \mathbb{R}^{L \times L}$ are the covariance matrix of $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0$ and $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_0^a$ respectively. Since \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{n} are white Gaussian noise, their mean over time is always zero. At time step k , the state \mathbf{x}_k^a can be estimated according to the algorithm in [20].

The correct setting of the Q and R matrices helps make the filters more robust. Usually, the process noise covariance matrix Q is determined using an innovation-based method [22], which relies on the difference between the actual measurement and the predicted position value from the system model. Conversely, the measurement noise covariance matrix R is often determined empirically, accounting for uncertainties in the tracking data. When empirical determination is not feasible, it is possible to assume a diagonal structure for R and estimate it from the knowledge of \mathbf{y} and \mathbf{x} as $R = I \cdot \|\varepsilon\|^2$, with $\|\varepsilon\|^2 = \|\mathbf{y} - H\mathbf{x}\|^2$, as discussed in [19].

B. Robust CBF-STL motion planning algorithm

In the case of a dynamic system with corrupted state information, the execution of a safe trajectory can be improved by using the estimated state derived from IV-A. In particular, the robust CBF-STL motion planning algorithm can be expressed from the QP in (6a), that ensures $\mathcal{C}(t)$ remains forward invariant, when $\mathbf{b}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t)$ is a vCBF, considering the estimated state $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$ from Sec. IV-A as follows:

$$\min_{\mathbf{u} \in \mathcal{U}} \mathbf{u}^T Q \mathbf{u} \quad (15a)$$

$$\text{s.t. } \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t)}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{x}}} (f(\hat{\mathbf{x}}) + g(\hat{\mathbf{x}})\mathbf{u}) + \frac{\partial \mathbf{b}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t)}{\partial t} \geq -\alpha(\mathbf{b}(\hat{\mathbf{x}}, t)),$$

$$\|v_x + v_y\| \leq v_{max}. \quad (15b)$$

In particular, we aim to minimize the control input \mathbf{u} while satisfying the following constraints: i) the CBF-STL constraint ensures task completion within a specified time interval. The function $\mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, leveraging the smooth approximation of the min operator in (5), incorporates both static and dynamic obstacle avoidance barriers, thereby enabling collision avoidance. In this case, the constraint includes the state estimate derived from UKF, as opposed to the approach used in [4], [6]; ii) the nonlinear velocity constraint, as we are interested in constraining the velocity norm, which requires

the quadratic norm of the omnidirectional robot's velocities to be less than or equal to v_{max} .

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

To validate the proposed approach, we consider a scenario in which an omnidirectional robot is in a social environment and needs to guide a person to various points of interest (e.g., $\mathbf{x}_{pose.1} = (8; 2)$ and $\mathbf{x}_{pose.2} = (5; 13)$). The simulation environment includes two static and two dynamic obstacles. Hence, the robot must plan and execute a collision-free path with the ability to reprogram its trajectory, reduce its speed in proximity of obstacles, or accelerate in obstacle-free areas. Moreover, we assume that depending on the robot's position, the velocity constraint v_{max} can vary, creating different operational modes: i) *Standard mode*: the default mode; ii) *Reduction mode*: when the robot is close to dynamic or static obstacles; iii) *Speed mode*: when the robot is going on a path free of obstacles. Arbitrarily, we set $v_{max} = \{1.5; 1.05; 3\}$ m/s for the different modes, respectively.

Additionally, we assume the initial position of the robot is known, and we consider that the robot must satisfy the following STL specification:

$$\phi = \phi_1 U_{[15,45]} \phi_2, \quad (16)$$

where:

$$\phi_1 = G_{[15,18]}(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{pose.1}\| \leq \varepsilon),$$

$$\phi_2 = F_{[18,45]}(\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}_{pose.2}\| \leq \varepsilon). \quad (17)$$

In particular, (16) defines the conjunction of the two specifications, ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 , in (17). The first specification, ϕ_1 , requires the robot to reach pose $\mathbf{x}_{pose.1} = (8; 2)$ with a tolerance $\varepsilon = 0.2$ m, within 15 s, and remain in that position until 18 s. Then, ϕ_2 , requires the robot to reach pose $\mathbf{x}_{pose.2} = (5; 13)$ with tolerance $\varepsilon = 0.2$ m within 45 s.

To evaluate the proposed framework, we simulated an SRN application in Gazebo using ROS2 Humble across three different use cases, as demonstrated in the accompanying video¹. In the first scenario, the ideal case without disturbances is considered, following the methodology outlined in [4]. In the second scenario, disturbances are introduced, resulting in localization uncertainties for the robot, again employing the methodology from [4]. In the third scenario, we build on the second case by applying the robust CBF-STL motion planning algorithm proposed in this work. The layout of the Gazebo simulation is depicted in Fig. 1, while Fig. 2 shows the 2D layout, with the colored areas representing the robot's three different operational modes.

Assuming an ideal scenario with no disturbances in the state measurement, and applying the framework described in [4], we obtain the results presented in Fig. 3. In particular, the satisfaction of the ϕ specification is indicated by the fact that the robot reaches the first destination in about 11 s, and leaves for the second destination at the time of 18 s, arriving within 45 s. In addition, the adherence of

¹DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13768594>

Fig. 1. Gazebo simulation of the considered environment, where we placed two static and two dynamic obstacles (black cylinders and humans)

Fig. 2. Robot's path is shown in black, the paths of the dynamic obstacles are shown in blue, the static obstacle positions are depicted in red, while the orange rectangles represent the areas where the robot must operate in reduction mode, the green areas represent where the robot must be in speed mode, and the white areas indicate the default mode

the velocity constraints and the positivity of the barrier are ensured.

In the real scenario, we consider the use of a robot location sensor that introduces uncertainty into the state measurements. Specifically, we assume that the sensor provides the robot's position with a uniform error distribution between -0.05 and 0.05 m. The results presented in Fig. 4 were obtained by applying the methodology described in [4]. These results demonstrate the satisfaction of the specification in (16) and conformity to speed constraints; however, the constant positivity of the barrier is not guaranteed. In particular, the top image in Fig. 4 shows that the robot has

Fig. 3. Considering the ideal case, the top plot shows the robot's speed in black, while the maximum allowed speed is shown in red. The second plot depicts the barrier value in black, which does not fall below the constraint boundary shown in red

Fig. 4. Considering the real case with a uniform error distribution between -0.05 and 0.05 m, in the top image, the robot's speed is shown in black, while the maximum allowed speed is shown in red. In the second image, the barrier value is depicted in black while the constraint barrier boundary is shown in red

continuous speed spikes, caused by disturbances, resulting in problems with energy consumption and negative user experience. An important point to note is that the small disturbance in the algorithm proposed in [4] does not ensure a safe trajectory execution.

This issue can be addressed using the method proposed in this work, with the results illustrated in Fig. 5. In the UKF, T_s has been chosen as the reciprocal of the QP simulation execution frequency equal to 20 ms. Q and R are computed as follows: Euler's method was used to predict the robot's future position in the first case, with no measurement error assumed. The resulting position deviation was 0.01 m. To reflect this deviation in the process noise covariance matrix

Fig. 5. Considering the real case with the proposed approach, in the top image, the robot’s speed is shown in black, while the maximum allowed speed is shown in red. In the second image, the barrier value is depicted in black while the constraint barrier boundary is shown in red

Q , the variance was calculated as the square of the deviation value. Therefore, a variance of 0.0001 was assigned to the diagonal elements of the Q matrix to accurately represent the predicted uncertainty in the robot’s position. Assuming the uniformly distributed noise, as described in the second case, the variance terms of the R matrix, which are equal to the square of the disturbance value, were determined to be 0.0025. In particular, Fig. 5 shows the satisfaction of the specification ϕ as well as adherence to speed constraints and barrier positivity in the case of uncertainties in measurements of the state. Moreover, the mean distance between the corrupted observed state and the true position obtained from Gazebo, x_{real} , in the second case, is equal to 0.038, while the mean distance between the estimated state \hat{x} and x_{real} , in the third case, is equal to 0.018. This difference highlights the significant reduction in errors achieved by the proposed method compared to the method presented in [4] when the state is subject to measurement noise.

VI. CONCLUSION

We proposed a robust CBF-STL motion planning methodology designed to mitigate the effects of state disturbances and measurement noise, ensuring task completion at any time within a specified time interval for dynamic systems subject to nonlinear velocity constraints and collision avoidance. This approach leverages UKF to compute accurate estimations of the perturbed state. We compared our performance with three different cases to evaluate the proposed framework, demonstrating its robustness in the presence of state measurement errors. In the future, we plan to implement the proposed approach in a robot in order to test this methodology in a real environment.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Holland, L. Kingston, C. McCarthy, E. Armstrong, P. O’Dwyer, F. Merz, and M. McConnell. Service robots in the healthcare sector. *Robot.*, 2021.
- [2] B. G. Draghici, A. E. Dobre, M. Misaros, and O. P. Stan. Development of a human service robot application using pepper robot as a museum guide. In *Int. Conf. on Autom., Quality and Testing, Robot.* IEEE, 2022.
- [3] R. Triebel, K. Arras, R. Alami, L. Beyer, S. Breuers, R. Chatila, M. Chetouani, D. Cremers, V. Evers, M. Fiore, et al. Spencer: A socially aware service robot for passenger guidance and help in busy airports. In *Field and Service Robot.: Results of the 10th Int. Conf.* Springer, 2016.
- [4] A. Ruo, L. Sabattini, and V. Villani. Cbf-based motion planning for socially responsible robot navigation guaranteeing stl specification. In *Eur. Conf. Control*, 2024.
- [5] K. Song, Y. Chiu, L. Kang, S. Song, C. Yang, P. Lu, and S. Ou. Navigation control design of a mobile robot by integrating obstacle avoidance and lidar slam. In *Int. Conf. on Syst., Man, and Cybern.* IEEE, 2018.
- [6] A. Ruo, L. Sabattini, and V. Villani. Cbf-based stl motion planning for social navigation in crowded environment. In *Eur. Robotic Forum*, 2024.
- [7] A. Francis, C. Pérez-d’Arpino, C. Li, F. Xia, A. Alahi, R. Alami, A. Bera, A. Biswas, J. Biswas, R. Chandra, et al. Principles and guidelines for evaluating social robot navigation algorithms. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2306.16740*, 2023.
- [8] F. Rollo, A. Zunino, G. Raiola, F. Amadio, A. Ajoudani, and N. Tsagarakis. Followme: a robust person following framework based on visual re-identification and gestures. In *Int. Conf. on Adv. Robot. and Its Social Impacts (ARSO)*. IEEE, 2023.
- [9] A. Ruo, L. Sabattini, and V. Villani. Follow me: an architecture for user identification and social navigation with a mobile robot. In *Eur. Robotic Forum*, 2024.
- [10] O. Maler and D. Nickovic. Monitoring temporal properties of continuous signals. In *Int. Symp. Formal Tech. in Real-Time and Fault-Tolerant Syst.* Springer, 2004.
- [11] L. Lindemann and D. V Dimarogonas. Control barrier functions for signal temporal logic tasks. *Control Syst. letters*, 2018.
- [12] L. Lindemann and D. V Dimarogonas. Barrier function based collaborative control of multiple robots under signal temporal logic tasks. *Transactions on Control of Netw. Syst.*, 2020.
- [13] A. D. Ames, S. Coogan, M. Egerstedt, G. Notomista, K. Sreenath, and P. Tabuada. Control barrier functions: Theory and applications. In *18th Eur. control Conf. (ECC)*. IEEE, 2019.
- [14] R. K. Cosner, A. W. Singletary, A. J. Taylor, T. G. Molnar, K. L. Bouman, and A. D. Ames. Measurement-robust control barrier functions: Certainty in safety with uncertainty in state. In *Int. Conf. on Intell. Robots and Syst.* IEEE, 2021.
- [15] M. Jankovic. Robust control barrier functions for constrained stabilization of nonlinear systems. *Automatica*, 2018.
- [16] R. Takano and M. Yamakita. Robust constrained stabilization control using control lyapunov and control barrier function in the presence of measurement noises. In *Conf. on Control Technol. and Appl.* IEEE, 2018.
- [17] A. Clark. Control barrier functions for stochastic systems. *Automatica*, 2021.
- [18] E. Bartocci, J. Deshmukh, A. Donzé, G. Fainekos, O. Maler, D. Ničković, and S. Sankaranarayanan. Specification-based monitoring of cyber-physical systems: a survey on theory, tools and applications. *Lectures on Runtime Verification: Introductory and Adv. Topics*, 2018.
- [19] F. Bianchi, S. Formentin, and L. Piroddi. Process noise covariance estimation via stochastic approximation. *Int. Journal of Adaptive Control and Signal Process.*, 2020.
- [20] E. A. Wan and R. Van Der Merwe. The unscented kalman filter. *Kalman filtering and neural networks*, 2001.
- [21] J. C. Butcher. *Numerical methods for ordinary differential equations*. John Wiley & Sons, 2016.
- [22] S. Akhlaghi, N. Zhou, and Z. Huang. Adaptive adjustment of noise covariance in kalman filter for dynamic state estimation. In *power & energy society general meeting*. IEEE, 2017.